

**Bridging the security, privacy, and data protection gap for
smaller enterprises in Europe**

D8.5 The SENTINEL QA plan & periodic monitoring report - first version

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
CA	Consortium Agreement
DEM	Dissemination and Exploitation Manager
DoA	Description of Action
EAB	External Advisory Board
EC	European Commission
EDAC	Ethics and Data privacy Advisory Committee
GA	General Assembly
IP	Intellectual Property
MoM	Minutes of Meeting
PC	Project Coordinator
PCC	Project Coordination Committee
PO	Project Officer
PTC	Project Technical Committee
QA	Quality Assurance
STIM	Scientific-Technical-Innovation Manager
ToC	Table of Contents
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The Quality Assurance plan is an internal document of the SENTINEL project, which is delivered in the context of Work Package 8, (*“Project Management, Coordination and Quality Assurance”*), under the task T8.1: “Project Quality Planning and Monitoring”. Quality procedures deal with:

- control actions planned
- time schedules
- requirement specifications and quality objectives
- responsibilities and authorities
- development, quality, testing, configuration, acceptance and maintenance plans
- agreed definitions of procedures for acceptance and quality control
- appropriate tools for planning, monitoring and progress reporting

In addition, this task (T8.1) deals with:

- identifying risk items using a structured and consistent approach to ensure that all areas are addressed
- quantitatively assessing the risk and ranking of items to establish those of most concern
- defining alternative paths of minimizing risks and criteria to initiate or terminate these activities
- monitoring and managing risks throughout the project’s life with Milestones reviewed and re-assessed

This document describes the quality processes and procedures together with measures to conduct periodic monitoring and can be viewed as complementing the Description of Action (DoA) and Consortium Agreement (CA) with respect to quality assessment. The Quality Management plan is being implemented by all project members to deliver and maintain quality throughout the project. This document also describes the information sharing process and electronic repository rules, document templates and related conventions. In order to ensure the quality of deliverables, this document describes the deliverable quality assurance process and rules for the production and review of deliverables.

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the Document

The main purpose of this document is to define the quality assurance including criteria, methods, tools and formal procedures towards achieving high quality outcomes in the SENTINEL project.

The QA plan procedures described in this document are in accordance with the SENTINEL Grant Agreement.

1.2 Structure of the Document

The document is divided into three main sections:

- Section 1 contains an introduction to the document
- Section 2 gives a general overview of the project organisation defining the roles and responsibilities for each of the project bodies. This section also covers the project communication, describing the general guidelines in the form of rules for the organisation of meetings.
- Section 3 describes the quality assurance procedures affecting mainly the project documents. The document management is explained and the deliverable review process is defined.

1.3 Intended readership

This document is intended for all consortium members, since it comprises a set of guidelines that accompanies the DoA and CA documents and must be implemented by all project members in order to ensure high quality of all project outcomes and smooth implementation of the project through efficient project management.

2. Project Organisation

2.1 Project governance

The project governance is the management framework which defines how the project decisions must be taken and indicates the structure including specific bodies, their roles and responsibilities and the way they interact during the lifecycle of the project.

2.1.1 Management Structure

The overall management structure is presented in the following figure:

Figure 1. SENTINEL's Project Management Structure.

2.1.2 General Assembly (GA)

Management representatives of all partners form the General Assembly (GA), which is the highest decision board of SENTINEL. The GA has the overall responsibility for all technical, financial, legal, administrative, ethical, IP management and dissemination issues of SENTINEL. The GA convenes at least every six months or, if necessary, more frequently to guarantee project progress and is chaired by the Project Coordinator. The GA a) assumes the overall management responsibility on behalf of the partners, b) takes decisions and approves changes in the work-

plan, resource allocation, deliverables, CA, etc., c) approves deliverables submission and d) reviews the project as a whole.

2.1.3 Project Coordinator (Dr. George Bravos, ITML)

The Project Coordinator (PC) is responsible for the coordination activities under the Grant Agreement signed with the EC. The PC interacts with the EC and third parties as a central contact point with regard to project management as well as administrative, technical, and scientific matters (or other activities following the Grant Agreement and its annexes), including the submission of the deliverables to the EC. In addition to his obligations under the Grant Agreement, the PC is responsible for receiving, compiling and distributing to all beneficiaries the documents, the reports, statements of expenditures and minutes of meetings of Plenaries and GA meetings, as well as any other information received from contributors. He is also responsible for monitoring the risk registry and managing the project risks in cooperation with the Scientific-Technical-Innovation Manager (STIM) and overseeing SENTINEL's ethical compliance.

138 *8kw – 207.65 *12kw 203.

2.1.4 Quality Assurance Manager (Dr. Tatiana Trantidou, ITML)

The Quality Assurance Manager (QAM) is responsible for overseeing the quality of the project tasks and deliverables. Specifically, for:

- a) Formulating a detailed Quality Control Strategy and Criteria for each project deliverable
- b) Assuring the conformity of deliverables with the criteria initial set for them, and
- c) Guaranteeing that deliverables are aligned with the Technical Annex of the proposal.

Each deliverable must be handed to the QAM, who in turn is responsible for forwarding it to two appointed reviewers (members of the consortium) for the established peer review process. If there is no consensus by the reviewers on the quality of the deliverable, corrective actions will be proposed in the consolidated review report, based on a synthesis of the two aforementioned individual peer reviews, which will be provided by the QAM.

The QAM is responsible for developing, implementing, communicating, and maintaining the quality plan throughout the lifecycle of the project. Moreover, the QAM is responsible for identifying problems during internal audits and initiating corrective actions to eliminate them. The QAM also ensures that goals and guidelines set by the Project Technical Committee (PTC) and the GA are implemented throughout the project.

2.1.5 Scientific-Technical-Innovation Manager (Dr. Artemios Geromitsos, INTRA)

The Scientific-Technical-Innovation Manager (STIM) works closely with the PC and is responsible for the overall technical project management and coordination of the work packages. The STIM a) ensures the scientific and technical cohesion and excellence of the project, b) oversees the organisation of technical workshops and meetings, c) proposes the agenda of technical workshops and meetings, d) supervises the quality of the deliverables produced by the WPs and e) cooperates with the PC to align SENTINEL's strategic objectives with the GA. The STIM also

pays special attention to the management of architectural harmonisation, integration, and standardisation. Finally, the STIM coordinates and monitors the outcomes of SENTINEL technical processes and to match them with business opportunities.

2.1.6 Dissemination and Exploitation Manager (Mr. Ruben Costa, UNINOVA)

The Dissemination and Exploitation Manager (DEM) is responsible for the dissemination and exploitation activities during the project lifecycle, as described in detail in WP7. Typical tasks of the DEM include but are not limited to:

- Ensuring project findings are systematically and efficiently disseminated to all possible interested actors and parties;
- Identifying relevant stakeholders that might be interested in the project results;
- Identifying appropriate channels and platforms to reach the intended audiences;
- Creating and distributing the SENTINEL's print and digital dissemination material;
- Creating and administering SENTINEL's social network channels;
- Providing material for the SENTINEL website (mostly for the News & Events section) – see Deliverable document D7.1 (submitted in M2);
- Organising SENTINEL's events and meetings.

Regarding exploitation, the DEM works closely with the leader of task T7.3 “Exploitation and standardization activities and practices towards a holistic privacy-by-design European solution” and coordinate issues relating to exploitation of results. More specifically, the DEM:

- Manages the knowledge produced during the project lifecycle with the goal of successfully implementing innovative ideas, assessing the opportunity for applying for patents and allowing the consortium to respond to potential external or internal opportunities;
- Supervises the preparation of the exploitation activities reports, including a detailed business plan which will be revised and updated to incorporate feedback from third parties;
- Make recommendations to the GA on issues of exploitation, including warnings in case of inconsistencies with the market goals;
- Address the market requirements to the technological and business potential created by SENTINEL, and
- Align the activities across work packages towards developing mutual benefit.

2.1.7 Project Technical Committee

The Project Technical Committee (PTC) is responsible for making and overseeing technical decisions made in the project. It has the power to directly control all tasks through partner consensus. The PTC is responsible for putting into place mechanisms which ensure quality of work for produced deliverables and any technical papers produced within the WP. The PTC consists of one delegate from each organisation participating in the project. To minimise management overload, partners acting as WP leaders are represented by the same persons in the PTC. The chairperson of the PTC is the project's STIM.

2.1.8 Ethics & Data privacy Advisory Committee (EDAC - CECL)

The main goals of the Ethics & Data privacy Advisory Committee (EDAC) are to:

- ensure that personal rights are respected
- understand potential uses of user information requirements
- ensure that deliverables and innovation activities meet European, national legal and ethical requirements
- identify and address any ethical issues rising from the research methodology
- identify and address any ethical issues rising from the research impact
- identify guidance and regulations with which SENTINEL should comply as the following:
 - Data protection Policy
 - Informed Consent Form policy
 - ETSI guidance notes
 - ISO/IEC 17799 Data security
 - Raise awareness of any privacy and security issues in SENTINEL
 - Monitor compliance

The EDAC is chaired by CECL and consists of 2-3 members of the consortium and further external experts. The EDAC is chaired by **Prof. Fereniki Panagopoulou**, who is Assistant Professor of Constitutional Law at Panteion University (Athens, Greece) with a proven track record on Data Protection Law, Bioethics and Medical Ethics.

Experts that confirmed their participation in SENTINEL's EDAC are:

- **Dr. Christopher Konialis** is a member of the project consortium – the founder of CG – with more than 35 years of experience in medical genetics and genomics.
- **Dr. Tal Soffer** (external) is the Head of the unit of Technology and Society Foresight at Tel Aviv University (Israel) with expertise in privacy and ethics rising from emerging technologies.

2.1.9 Work Package Leader (WPL)

For every work package, there is a person designated as Work Package Leader (WPL) whose task is to coordinate WP work and ensure that activities within the work package are carried out in a timely manner and deliverables are submitted within schedule. All partners contributing effort in each WP are coordinated by the WPL in the detailed planning and execution of work carried out at the task level. The WPL must coordinate the interaction and collaboration with other WPLs to facilitate communication within and between interdependent WPs.

2.1.10 Task Leader (TL)

The person designated as Task Leader (TL) coordinates work at the task level, organised in the same way as at the WP level (WPL). The TL is appointed by the partner leading a task, as defined in each work package and coordinates the task work among the task participants.

2.1.11 External Advisory Board (EAB)

The project has formed an External Advisory Board (EAB) consisting of relevant external stakeholders from any industry related to the management of sensitive data in the public and private sectors. The EAB will follow the development of the project and will a) provide feedback to ensure that the scientific and technological evolution of the project is on-track to fulfil its stated goals, and b) provide an external global viewpoint to ensure that the project's research and development targets and activities are appropriate for producing significant advancements beyond the state-of-the-art.

The EAB gives the project access to advice from external experts from relevant domains, widens the scope of innovation and helps establish future exploitation pathways. The constituent assembly of EAB has been defined in the first two months of the project execution. The EAB will participate once a year in a project meeting or review. EAB members will be finalised within the first 3 months of the project. The experts invited to the EAB who have already accepted the invitation are:

- **Mr Rodrigo Diaz**, Head of Cybersecurity Unit in ATOS Research & Innovation department, Barcelona, Spain.
- **Mr Toomas Lepik**, Senior Information Security expert, SME owner of IT Kool Ja Konsultatsioonid OÜ, Brussels, Belgium.
- **Prof. João Mendonça**, Ass. Professor in the Department of mechanical Engineering at the University of Minho (Portugal) with a strong link with SMEs.
- **Mr Stephanos Camarinopoulos**, Director in RISA Sicherheitsanalysen GmbH, Berlin, Germany.

2.2 Project Communications

Communication between project partners is one of the most important aspects for a successful project that will deliver outcomes according to expectations and initially set objectives. The rules that place the foundation for the above are:

- Several regular official meetings
- Meetings organized according to the current needs of the project. Before the meeting, an agenda will be shared to the partners containing key aspects to be covered. After the meeting, the person organizing the meeting will share minutes of meeting (MoM) concluding important information shared within the meeting's context and the relevant action list will be circulated among the consortium, with all partners having the right for changes and/or suggestions.
- A project mail list has been created containing all members of the consortium to facilitate communication among partners for technical-, work package- or other- related purposes.
- A Cloud information and files sharing environment (SENTINEL NextCloud), so that the consortium members can have access to all project information.
- Project and document templates (presentations, deliverables, agendas, peer reviews, etc.) to ensure uniformity of information presentation and identification of documents.

2.2.1.1 Project meetings

Project meetings are used to keep all partners in line with the *current* project status and objectives, as well as increase the efficiency of collective decision making. Emails and teleconferences will be used for everyday communication, while phone calls can be used as well in case of emergencies or as an alternative communication medium.

General directions for the organisation of meetings are:

- Before a planned meeting (GA, plenary, etc.) an adequate notice will be given to allow the participants to prepare and manage any logistics issues. For meetings that require physical presence, agenda and meeting notice must be sent at least 4 weeks (30 calendar days) preceding the meeting. For virtual meetings, the agenda and notice must be sent 1 week before (7 calendar days).
- The duration and venue of the meeting must be communicated beforehand.
- Notice for the meeting must include a draft version of the agenda with the main aspects to be discussed. After participants agree on the agenda, refinements can be done with any additions of topics not mentioned in the draft.
- MoM will be produced by the chairperson (or member of the chairperson's organisation) of the meeting and communicated to the attendees no later than two weeks (14 calendar days) after the meeting. The minutes will be considered as accepted if there are no objections in written form within 1 week (7 calendar days) from the meeting. MoM should include:
 - Attendance list
 - Agenda (or link to the agenda in the project's electronic repository)
 - Main discussion points
 - List of action points
 - Next steps (with dates if possible)
 - One or more photo(s) (or print screens) of the meeting with as many participants as possible

2.2.1.2 General Assembly meetings

GA meetings are chaired by the PC and cover project aspects of technical and non-technical nature. The meeting aims to exchange technical status and information, prepare for interim reporting and reviews, share project progress amongst partners and provide information on next steps and actions to follow. The GA will hold physical or virtual meetings at least four times a year (physical meetings can be combined with other meetings). Ad hoc meetings can take place as well if deemed necessary.

2.2.1.3 Project Technical Committee meetings

Project Technical Committee (PTC) meetings are chaired by the STIM and will cover technical aspects, as the project progresses. The meeting aims to build a solid foundation from the beginning of the project, on which technology developments will step and move forwards, review

the overall progress, revise the risk register, as well as update the Data Management Plan and dissemination plans, inter-WP collaboration. The PTC will schedule physical or virtual meetings at least four times a year (physical meetings can be combined with other meetings), but it is advised to meet via teleconference monthly. Minutes from the PTC meetings will be forwarded to the consortium within 5 working days after each collaborating event.

2.2.1.4 Work package meetings

Work package meetings are to be used by WP partners to coordinate work and exchange information. These meetings are to be called by the WPL (or coordinator) and include the WPL, TLs and any other partner deemed useful on the related topic. The schedule of these meetings is decided by the WPL, but it is advised to meet via teleconference at least once a month.

2.3 Project Reporting procedures

The reporting procedures for the project follow the terms and conditions detailed in the Grant Agreement. In general, SENTINEL accommodates quality management by regular project reporting of all partners, which is utilised as input for the project reports to the Project Officer (PO) and the European Commission (EC). SENTINEL employs continuous reporting to the EC via its web-based project management portal. Henceforth, WPLs will provide short reports regarding the related WP activities and achievements to the PC at the end of each quarter (September, January and May). Then, the PC will consolidate the material and do the continuous reporting (online). Such reports would contain progress report (against baseline), resources, achievements, and risks. The content for the relevant reporting deliverables (D8.1-D8.4, D8.6-D8.7) is based on this information, as well as specific information on closed, active or upcoming WPs directly given by the corresponding WP leaders.

Detailed technical content and detailed progress information for each WP will be reported from TLs towards the relevant WPL. Thereafter, the WPL will inform the PTC accordingly.

3. Quality Assurance

Quality assurance (QA) aims to formulate a framework for project deliverables, documents and output in general to be in conformity with the Grant Agreement and to achieve the expected quality. Quality assurance will be performed in all project phases through WP8 by the PC that will secure SENTINEL quality and relevant documentation at all development stages of the project. SENTINEL will adopt the widely accepted *Plan-Do-Check-Act* (PDCA) principle to achieve proper monitoring of project activities. Through the PDCA principle, all work done within WPs and tasks will be closely monitored on a continuous basis, resulting in initiated corrective actions and changes to the project plan when necessary.

Two main processes are described below:

- Document management process, which described the rules to be followed in order to produce and manage project deliverables (Plan-Do);
- Deliverable review, which describes the process that ensures deliverables produced are equivalent to the quality standards defined by the project (Check-Act).

3.1 Document management process

The document management process defines the language used within the documents, the storage methods and the format each deliverable must follow, and provides reference to the project template, which should be used in the creation of all project documents.

3.1.1 Language

Language in all documents (e.g., technical and financial reports) and deliverables is English, following appropriate grammar rules and formal language. Dissemination material like newsletters, press releases, fliers, etc., will be produced in English as well, although it can be localized/translated, when needed.

3.1.2 Storage

The project has made an electronic repository (NextCloud) available to partners, which is to be used as a main tool for sharing information amongst partners. All shareable project information will be stored and kept up to date there. The QAM has created a specific folder structure, which will be maintained by all partners and followed by WPLs and TLs in the respective WP folders. The QAM has been assigned to keep the general maintenance of the repository, e.g. creating folders, adding or deleting users, etc.

The structure of the electronic repository aims to be clear and comprehensive by all partners and it is designed to facilitate internal work and collaboration.

- 01_Contact list: Contains an excel file with all participants latest contact details, who also populate the project's mailing list. The folder also contains a dedicated excel spreadsheet with information about main and secondary contact points from each member organisation for the General Assembly, as well as about leading and deputy partner contact details regarding WP and task leadership.
- 02_Contract Documents: Contains all the appropriate documents of the project contract, specifically the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement.
- 03_Meetings: Contains information from the project meetings, such as the agenda, presentations, MoM and any other relevant material.
- 04_Deliverables Final: Contains the pdf documents of all deliverables that are finalized and submitted to the EC.
- 05_Dissemination: Contains all the documents and material relevant to the various dissemination and communication processes of the project.
- 06_Templates: Contains all projects templates, so that they are used by all partners.

- Work Packages (9 folders in total): Contains one folder per WP of the project with relevant material.

Each WP folder has the following structure:

- 01_Organisation: Contains information relevant to the organisation of the specific WP, e.g., contact points for the specific WP, WP plan, etc.
- 02_Meetings: Contains information from the specific WP meetings, such as presentations, MoM and any other relevant material.
- 03_Reports: Contains report documents from each reporting period with collected material from the specific WP only.
- 04_Deliverables: Contains material relevant to the preparation of deliverables for the specific WP.
- Tasks folder: Contains one folder per task within the specific WP of the project with relevant material.

3.1.3 Document Format

The deliverable author should make sure that all deliverable versions, excluding final, are named according to the following format:

SENTINEL_Dx.y_Deliverabletitle_Vx

Where:

- SENTINEL: project's short name
- Dx.y: Deliverable number as described in the DoA (e.g., D1.1)
- Deliverable title: The name of the deliverable as it can be found in the DoA (e.g., D8.5_Quality_Assurance_plan_and_periodic_monitoring_report_first_version)
- Vx: The version of the file (e.g., SENTINEL_D8.5_Quality_Assurance_plan_and_periodic_monitoring_report_first_version_V1)

The underscore (_) between words is necessary to activate linking of the filename.

3.1.4 References

An example of bibliography references can be found in the references section of this document.

3.1.5 Templates

All partners should base their project documents on the following templates that can be found in the electronic repository of the project:

- SENTINEL_Presentation_template.pptx
- SENTINEL_Agenda_template.docx (see Appendix A)
- SENTINEL_Deliverable_template.docx

- SENTINEL_Peer_review_document.docx (see Appendix A)
- SENTINEL_MoM_template.docx (see Appendix A)

If necessary, other templates will be produced accordingly.

3.2 Deliverable Review

Deliverable peer review aims to ensure that deliverables being submitted conform to the highest quality standards as defined in the Grant Agreement.

3.2.1 Deliverable review planning

As a first step for the deliverable review process, the QAM has created a peer review planning document (see Appendix B). This document should be monitored by all partners, so that they can keep track of their responsibilities for reviewing deliverables. The document lists all project deliverables and assigns two organisations as peer reviewers *per deliverable*, based on the following criteria:

- **Partners' effort:** The number of reviews assigned to each partner is directly proportional to the effort the organisation has in the project.
- **Involvement in the deliverable creation:** The organisation assigned for a peer review cannot be directly involved with the creation of the deliverable.
- **Involvement in the project:** The person assigned as a reviewer should have knowledge of the project and ideally is a person working on the project. However, as mentioned above, the person should not directly be involved with the creation of the deliverable.

3.2.2 Roles and responsibilities

The roles and responsibilities of the entities involved in the peer review are listed in the table below:

Table 1. SENTINEL's Roles & Responsibilities

Role	Responsibility
Coordinator	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Formally approve the version to be sent to the EC
Quality Assurance Manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Responsible for the review process, establishing deadlines, contacting the peer reviewers and coordinating the overall procedure▪ Support the reviews, if needed▪ Consolidate the 2 peer review forms in 1 final per peer review form

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Evaluate the deliverable and approve the version to be sent to the coordinator ▪ Ensure the files are uploaded on the electronic repository
Scientific-Technical-Innovation Manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ If needed, support the QAM with the technical aspects of the deliverable when reviewing the document ▪ Approve the technical aspects of the documents, before it is sent to the coordinator
Deliverable Leader	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Process the peer reviews and address the comments made from the peer reviewers ▪ Approve the version to be sent to the coordinator
Deliverable Team	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Support the Deliverable leader in addressing the comments made by the peer reviewers as per the instructions of the Deliverable Leader
Peer Reviewer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Carefully and thoroughly examine the deliverable in terms of content and format following the guidelines of the peer review evaluation form.

3.2.3 Deliverable review process

The following steps of the deliverable review process are not formal, so they can be adjusted accordingly. During this process, it is highly recommended that the electronic repository (NextCloud) is used for the exchange of documents.

Table 2. SENTINEL Deliverable review process

Step	Role	Responsibility	Timeline*
1	Deliverable Leader	▪ Sets up the deliverable structure – Table of Contents (ToC)	>2 months
		▪ Contacts the contributors and coordinates the creation of the deliverable	
		▪ Sends the draft to the work package leader for a 1 st review	>1 month
2	Work Package Leader	▪ Evaluates the deliverable and either accepts it and forwards it to the QAM for peer review or returns it back to the Deliverable Leader with recommendations	>2 weeks to 1 month
3	Deliverable Leader	▪ Addresses any feedback from the WPL and sends the latest version to the QAM	
4	Quality Manager	▪ Evaluates the deliverable and either forwards it to the pre-assigned peer reviewers or returns it to the Deliverable Leader with recommendations	>2 weeks to 1 month

** Timeline refers to months/weeks before deliverable due date.*

Once all the previous iterations are concluded and the final draft is ready, the QAM initiates the peer review process. The review process should be initiated **2 weeks to 1 month** before the official submission date (depending on the size and complexity of the deliverable, as well as the overall timeline, possible delays, etc.). The assignment plan of deliverable reviewers (as per M3 of the project) is presented in Appendix B. Assignments could slightly change as per the partners' availability or increased review needs, as the project progresses.

Conclusion

The SENTINEL's QA plan & periodic monitoring report aims to specify a) the procedures to be followed by the SENTINEL consortium in order to guarantee the highest possible quality for the project results expected by the European Commission and b) describe the overall management and monitoring procedures. The templates mentioned in Section 3.1.5 of this document have been placed in the project's Cloud repository and include those for the deliverable document, presentation, peer review document, minutes of meeting, agenda and more. The proposed quality management methodologies are well defined and applicable to all project activities, thus allowing for accurate project monitoring and management. Compliance with these methodologies is mandatory for every SENTINEL partner.

References

- [1] Berkun S. (2008) Making Things Happen: Mastering Project Management (Theory in Practice). Massachusetts: O'Reilly Media.
- [2] Guide, A. (2001). Project management body of knowledge (pmbok® guide). In Project Management Institute.

Appendix A – Project templates

A.1 Peer review document

Overall Peer Review Result

Deliverable is:

<input type="checkbox"/> Fully accepted	<input type="checkbox"/> Accepted with minor comments	<input type="checkbox"/> Rejected unless modified as suggested	<input type="checkbox"/> Rejected
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Specific peer review criteria:

1. **Relevance** - “Is this deliverable relevant to SENTINEL and to the particular WP activities it covers?”
2. **Methodological framework soundness** - “Are the results arbitrary or based upon a clear methodology, involving users’ test, expert opinions, etc.?”
3. **Quality of achievements** – “Are the results of high value and as expected”?
4. **Quality of presentation of achievements** – “Are the results adequately explained and commented?”
5. **Deliverable layout / spelling / format** – “Does the deliverable include all necessary chapters; is it readable in comprehensive language, etc.?”

COMMENTS OF PEER REVIEWER

General comments

These refer to any issue not covered by the particular topics below. They may refer to thoroughness of general contents, correspondence of the reported work to the project’s objectives as in the Description of Action and correspondence to the general programme objectives.

A.2 SENTINEL Agenda template

Name of event/meeting

The logo for SENTINEL, featuring the word "SENTINEL" in a bold, sans-serif font. The letter 'S' is stylized with a red shield-like shape inside its top curve.

Bridging the security, privacy and data protection gap for smaller enterprises in Europe

AGENDA

xx month year

start_time-end_time CET

HORIZON 2020 WORK PROGRAMME 2018-2020

Call: H2020-SU-DS-2018-2020: Digital Security

Topic: SU-DS03-2019-2020 *Small and Medium-sized Enterprises and Micro Enterprises (SMEs&MEs): defenders of security, privacy and personal data protection*

Consortium: ITML, LIST, The Shell, IDIR, INTRA, STS, AEGIS, TSI, CCS, UNINOVA, CG, TIG, CECL, FP

Project No	101021659
Instrument	Innovation Action
Start Date	June 1 st , 2021
Duration	36 months
Coordinator	ITML

Registration and Coffee		
Session 1: Name of Session 1		
Moderator: Partner		
11:00 – 11:30	Coffee Break	
Session 2: Name of Session 2		
Moderator: Partner		
14:15 – 15:00	Lunch	
Session 3: Name of Session 3		
Moderator: Partner		
16:30 – 16:40	Break	
	Wrap-up, Next meeting, Issues, AOB	

Appendix B – Internal Review Planning

Del. No	Del. Title	WP	Leader	Type	Dissem.	Rev1	Rev2	Date	Status	Actual delivery
D1.1	The SENTINEL baseline	1	IDIR	R	PU	UNINOVA	ITML	09/2021		
D1.2	The SENTINEL technical architecture	1	INTRA	R	PU	ITML	TIG	11/2021		
D1.3	The SENTINEL experimentation protocol	1	IDIR	R	PU	THE SHELL	LIST	11/2021		
D2.1	The SENTINEL data protection and cybersecurity offerings: MVP	2	SHELL	DEM	PU	INTRA	CCS	05/2022		
D2.2	The SENTINEL data protection and cybersecurity offerings: 1 st complete version	2	FP	DEM	PU	UNINOVA	FP	11/2022		
D2.3	The SENTINEL data protection and cybersecurity offerings: Final version	2	LIST	DEM	PU	ITML	UNINOVA	11/2023		
D2.4	Continuous data privacy legislation compliance monitoring and guidelines – interim version	2	CECL	R	PU	INTRA	IDIR	11/2022		
D2.5	Continuous data privacy legislation compliance monitoring and guidelines – final version	2	CECL	R	PU	AEGIS	FP	11/2023		
D3.1	The SENTINEL digital core: MVP	3	SHELL	DEM	PU	CCS	TSI	05/2022		
D3.2	The SENTINEL data protection and cybersecurity offerings: 1 st complete version	3	FP	DEM	PU	CG	CCS	11/2022		
D3.3	The SENTINEL data protection and cybersecurity offerings: Final version	3	LIST	DEM	PU	TIG	UNINOVA	11/2023		
D4.1	The SENTINEL services: MVP	4	IDIR	DEM	PU	LIST	The SHELL	05/2022		

D8.5 The SENTINEL QA plan & periodic monitoring report - first version

D4.2	The SENTINEL data protection and cybersecurity offerings: 1 st complete version	4	STS	DEM	PU	The SHELL	ITML	11/2022		
D4.3	The SENTINEL data protection and cybersecurity offerings: Final version	4	ACS	DEM	PU	CG	CCS	11/2023		
D5.1	The SENTINEL visualisation and UI component – first version	5	AEGIS	DEM	PU	The SHELL	STS	05/2022		
D5.2	The SENTINEL visualisation and UI component – second version	5	AEGIS	DEM	PU	ITML	INTRA	11/2022		
D5.3	The SENTINEL visualisation and UI component – final version	5	AEGIS	DEM	PU	CCS	ITML	11/2023		
D5.4	The SENTINEL Minimum Viable Product	5	INTRA	R+DEM	PU	ITML	AEGIS	05/2022		
D5.5	The SENTINEL integrated solution – interim version	5	INTRA	R+DEM	PU	FP	IDIR	11/2022		
D5.6	The SENTINEL integrated solution – final version	5	INTRA	R+DEM	PU	LIST	TIG	11/2023		
D5.7	Best practices for maintaining and operating the system in the long-term – TRL 7	5	UNINOVA	R	PU	CG	The SHELL	05/2024		
D6.1	SENTINEL Demonstration - initial execution and evaluation	6	TIG	R	CO	ITML	IDIR	11/2022		
D6.2	SENTINEL Demonstration - final execution	6	CG	R	PU	FP	AEGIS	11/2023		
D6.3	Assessment report and impact analysis	6	STS	R	PU	TSI	LIST	05/2024		
D7.1	The SENTINEL website and visual identity	7	ITML	R+DEM	PU	UNINOVA	CECL	07/2021		
D7.2	Market analysis and preliminary business modelling	7	AEGIS	R	CO	INTRA	CCS	11/2021		
D7.3	Dissemination strategy and activities – interim version	7	UNINOVA	R	PU	ITML	AEGIS	11/2022		
D7.4	Dissemination strategy and activities – final version	7	UNINOVA	R	PU	STS	The SHELL	05/2024		
D7.5	Ecosystem building and SMEs engagement report – interim version	7	UNINOVA	R	PU	CECL	FP	11/2022		
D7.6	Ecosystem building and SMEs engagement report – final version	7	UNINOVA	R	PU	AEGIS	FP	05/2024		

D8.5 The SENTINEL QA plan & periodic monitoring report - first version

D7.7	Exploitation strategy, standardisation activities and best practices – interim version	7	STS	R	CO	INTRA	AEGIS	11/2022		
D7.8	Exploitation strategy, standardisation activities and best practices – final version	7	STS	R	CO	ITML	CCS	05/2024		
D7.9	Final business model, market analysis and long-term sustainability report	7	AEGIS	R	PU	IDIR	INTRA	05/2024		
D8.1	Yearly project management report – first version	8	ITML	R	PU	AEGIS	IDIR	05/2022		
D8.2	Yearly project management report – second version	8	ITML	R	PU	INTRA	The SHELL	05/2023		
D8.3	Yearly project management report – third version	8	ITML	R	PU	IDIR	STS	05/2024		
D8.4	Risk identification and management & quality plan	8	ITML	R	CO	TSI	IDIR	11/2021		
D8.5	The SENTINEL QA plan and periodic monitoring report – first version	8	ITML	R	PU	IDIR	AEGIS	08/2021		
D8.6	The SENTINEL QA plan and periodic monitoring report – second version	8	ITML	R	PU	FP	INTRA	11/2022		
D8.7	The SENTINEL QA plan and periodic monitoring report – final version	8	ITML	R	PU	INTRA	CECL	05/2024		
D8.8	The SENTINEL project handbook – first version	8	ITML	R	PU	CECL	INTRA	09/2021		
D8.9	The SENTINEL data management plan	8	ITML	ORDP	PU	TSI	STS	11/2021		
D8.10	The SENTINEL project handbook – first version	8	ITML	R	PU	CCS	IDIR	05/2022		
D8.11	The SENTINEL project handbook – first version	8	ITML	R	PU	STS	IDIR	05/2023		
D8.12	The SENTINEL technical and innovation management report – interim version	8	INTRA	R	CO	AEGIS	CCS	11/2022		

D8.5 The SENTINEL QA plan & periodic monitoring report - first version

D8.13	The SENTINEL technical and innovation management report – final version	8	INTRA	R	CO	The SHELL	STS	05/2024		
D8.14	Ethics manual and ethical controlling report – interim version	8	CECL	R	CO	ITML	FP	11/2022		
D8.15	Ethics manual and ethical controlling report – final version	8	CECL	R	CO	CG	LIST	05/2024		
D9.1	POPD – Requirement No. 1	9	ITML	Ethics	CO	CECL	FP	09/2021		